

EURO-CORDEX-CMIP6 RCM component description (v0.1, 2023-10-05)

institution_id	Model	Reference	Configuration	LBC update freq.	Nudging	Projection or coordinate system	Horizontal resolution	Nesting	Relaxation scheme	Full domain (no. of computational grid cells)	Buffer (no. Grid cells)	Model top height	No. of vertical levels	model time-step (dynamics)	Hydrostatic/non-hydrostatic	Radiation scheme	Greenhouse gases (species)	GHG evolution (interactive/non-interactive)	Convection scheme	Shallow Convection scheme	Microphysics scheme	
CNRM	ALADIN64	Nabat et al. 2020	RESM configuration, tuning on-going	6h	LBCs without SpectralNudging	Lambert conformal	12.5km	direct into GCM	according to Davies 1976	480x480 (C+H-E grid)	8 in every direction	75km, 0.01 hPa	91	450s	Hydrostatic	FMR-6bands, RRTM	CO2, N2O, CH4, CFC12 and a CFC11-equivalent species that includes the effects of all the other GHGs of the original data set (39 species).	yes not interactive	PCMT	PCMT	Lopez (2002)	
ICTP	RegCM5	Coppola et al. 2021	to be agreed	6h	LBCs	Lambert conformal	12km	direct GCM	exponential relaxation	530	40		41?				> In CMIP6 such information is	yes not interactive				
CLMcom - COSMO-CLM	COSMO-CLM	Rockel et al. (2008)	COPAT 2 configuration C2C317	6h	LBCs, model top	sphere, rotated pole	0.11° (450 x 438 grid boxes incl. boundary zone)	direct into GCM	Davies and Turner (1977), Stauffer and Seaman (1990)	450 x 438 grid boxes incl. boundary zone; 40 vertical levels, 9 soil levels	13	22.7 km	40	90 s	non-hydrostatic	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	SSP scenarios	yes (non-interactive)	Mass-flux shallow and deep (Tiedtke, 1989; Bechtold et al., 2008)	Mass-flux shallow and deep (Tiedtke, 1989; Bechtold et al., 2008)	Single-moment scheme incl. cloud ice scheme (Doms et al. 2004; Seifert et al. 2010)	
CLMcom - ICON-CLM	ICON-CLM	Pham et al. (2021)	to be agreed	6h	LBCs, model top	Icosahedron, unstructured grid	R13B05 (12.14 km); data will be provided on "rotated" 0.11° grid	direct into GCM	according to Davies (1976, 1983)	199920 (R13B05) about 454 x 442 on rotated 0.11° grid	15	23.5 km	60	100 s	non-hydrostatic	ecRad (Hogan and Bozzo, 2018)	SSP scenarios	yes (non-interactive)	Mass-flux shallow and deep (Tiedtke, 1989; Bechtold et al., 2008)	Mass-flux shallow and deep (Tiedtke, 1989; Bechtold et al., 2008)	Single-moment scheme (Doms et al. 2004; Seifert et al., 2010)	
KNMI	RACMO23E			6h	LBCs; NO nudging in interior	rotated pole	0.11°	direct from GCM		456x444 grid points	16		40	300s	yes		CO2, CH4, N2O, CFC11, CFC12, O3	yes, following SSPs				
MOHC	HadREM3-GA7.05	Tucker et al. 2021	to be agreed	6h	LBCs only, no nudging in the interior	rotated pole	0.11° x0.11°	direct	blending		10	39 km	63			SOCRATES	CO2, CH4, N2O, CFC-12 eq, HFC-134a eq, O3, H2O	yes not interactive (except H2O)	Gregory-Rowntree (1990), mass-flux	Gregory Rowntree (1990)	Wilson and Ballard (1999)	
GERICS	REMO2020	soon to be published, till then Jacob (2001)	to be agreed	6h	LBCs, no nudging	rotated pole	0.11°	direct	classical Davies procedure (Davies, 1976).	433x433	8	32km	49	60s	Hydrostatic	ECMWF-ECHAM4	CO2, CH4, N2O, CFC11, CFC12, O3	yes not interactive	Tiedtke (1989) + Nordeng (1996) + Pfeifer (2007); mass-flux	Tiedtke (1989) + Nordeng (1996) + Pfeifer (2007); mass-flux	Lohmann and Roeckner (1996) with some revisions, and a diagnostic cloud cover scheme (Sundqvist et al., 1989)	
RMIB-UGent	ALARO-0	Giot et al., 2016		6h	LBCs, no nudging	rotated pole	12.5km	direct	classical Davies procedure (Davies, 1976).	501x501	8		46	300s	Hydrostatic	ACRANE2 (Masek et al. 2016; Geleyn et al. 2017)		yes not interactive	3MT (Gerard et al. (2009))	TOUCANS (Duran et al. 2014)	Lopez (2002)	
CLMcom-FZJ	COSMO5-01-CLM3-5-0-ParFlow3-9-0	Rockel et al., 2008; Shrestha et al., 2014; Gasper et al., 2016	about final, in line with the CCLM_v5_0_clm6 reference for COSMO v5	3h	LBCs, no nudging	rotated pole	0.11°	direct into GCM	classical Davies procedure (Davies, 1976)	450x438	13	22km	50	100s	non-hydrostatic	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	CO2, CH4, N2O, O3	yes, not interactive	Tiedtke (1989)	Tiedtke (1989)	Kessler (1969) with cloud ice scheme	
HCLIMcom-SMHI, HCLIMcom-DMI, HCLIMcom-MetNo	HCLIM43-ALADIN	Belušić et al. 2020	HCLIM43_CORDEX6	6h	LBCs, no nudging	Lambert conformal	12.5km	direct	Davies	480x480	8	10 hPa (30 km)	65	450s	Hydrostatic	FMR-6bands (SW), RRTM (LW)	CO2, CH4, O3, CFC11, CFC12 and N2O	yes not interactive	Deep convection: Bougeault (1985)	Kain-Fritsch/Bechtold	Lopez (2002); Bouteloup et al. (2005)	
AUTH, NORCE/BCCR, CESAM, IDL, UCAN/IFCA, IMWM/CI TASK	WRF4.4.2 (t.b.d)	Skamarock et al. 2019	WRF442Q (t.b.d.)	6h (3hr discussed - t.b.d.)	LBCs, no nudging	rotated pole	0.11°	direct	following Davies and Turner (1977)	445x433	10	20hPa	54	60s	non-hydrostatic	RRTMG (Iacono et al. 2008)	CO2, CH4, CFC11, CFC12, N2O	yes not interactive	Kain-Fritsch(Kain-Fritsch)	no (bl_mynn_edmf =1, Olson et al. 2019)	Thompson scheme (Thompson et al., 2008)	
AUTH	WRF4.?	Skamarock et al. 2019	t.b.d.	6h	LBCs, no nudging	t.b.d	0.11°	tbd	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	tbd	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	non-hydrostatic	t.b.d.		yes not interactive	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	

institution_id	Model	Planetary boundary layer scheme	Land-surface scheme (dataset, interactive/non-interactive veg.)	Soil initialization and spin-up (temperature and moisture)	Soil depth 1-layer and total and number layers	Interactive Aerosols (yes/no)	Evolving Aerosols (yes/no, species, forcing dataset)	Solar constant	SST treatment (prescribed/coupled)	Sea ice treatment (prescribed or modeled)	Glacier treatment	Land use changes	Urban Scheme (yes/no and type)	Lake model (yes/no + informat)	Additional land-surface/sub-surface	Tuning strategy
CNRM	ALADIN64		SURFEX, interactive vegetation	2 years		yes	yes		prescribed	sea ice limit from GCM and interactive 1D sea ice model for ice characteristics such as surface temperature	no	to be decided. Tests ongoing	no (rock)	yes (FLAKE 1D)	yes, CTRIP for land hydrology	Machine-learning based approach called "history matching", adaptation to RCM of the approach described in Hourdin et al. 2021 (https://doi.org/10.1029/2020MS002225) and Couvreux et al. 2021 (https://doi.org/10.1029/2020MS002217)
ICTP	RegCM5				0.0175 m first; 3.802 m total	no	yes		prescribed	prescribed according to GCM limit	prescribed according to CML4.5	no	yes (no AC nor urban traffic)	yes (Hostette r single column)		
CLMcom - COSMO-CLM	COSMO-CLM	Prognostic TKE (Raschendorfer, 2001; Raupach and Shaw, 1981)	TERRA (Schrodin and Heise, 2001; Schulz et al., 2016) (Land use dataset: GlobCover; non-interactive veg.)	T interpol.from GCM SM by climatological mean from evaluation runs + 1 year spin-up	0,01 m first, 15.34 total, 10 layers	no	no		prescribed from GCM (likewise for sea-ice extent)	concentration prescribed, surface temperature and thickness modeled (Mironov et al., 2012)	no	no	no	FLake (Mironov, 2008)	no	COPAT2 (test different features that are available in the model first individually and perform combined tests of beneficial features afterwards. Tested features are based on expert judgement. No specific optimization of parameter values is performed.
CLMcom - ICON-CLM	ICON-CLM	Prognostic TKE (Raschendorfer, 2001; Raupach and Shaw, 1981)	Tiled TERRA (Schrodin and Heise, 2001; Schulz et al., 2016) (Land use dataset: GlobCover; non-interactive veg.)	T interpol.from GCM SM by climatological mean from evaluation runs + 1 year spin-up	0,01 m first, 21.87 total, 8 layers	no	t.b.d		prescribed from GCM (likewise for sea-ice extent)	concentration prescribed, surface temperature and thickness modeled (Mironov et al., 2012)	no	no	TERRA_URB, bulk (Schulz et al., 2022)	FLake (Mironov, 2008)	no	COPAT2 (test different features that are available in the model first individually and perform combined tests of beneficial features afterwards. Tested features are based on expert judgement. No specific optimization of parameter values is performed.
KNMI	RACMO23E						RACMO23 follows Ec-Earth3/Ec-Earth3-Veg with evolving aerosol: 1) MACV2-SP 2) TM5-PI for background; 3) stratospheric		prescribed from GCM (likewise for sea-ice extent)				no (bare soil)	yes (FLAKE 1D)		
MOHC	HadREM3-GA7.05	Lock et al 2001	JULES	t.b.d. (usually from climatology, one year spin-up)	0.1m, 2m, 4 layers	no	yes. MACV2-SP: not ready to scale to GCM AOD	11 year solar cycle	prescribed from GCM (also sea-ice)	prescribed		disturbed fraction only	no	no		
GERICS	REMO2020	Louis (1979)	Schulz et al. (2001)	t.b.d.	for temperatures 0.065 m, 9.834m, 5 layers	no	yes. MACV2-SP by default; also ready for external forcing. Also supports MERRA climatology for evaluation and GCM AOD forcing for scenarios		prescribed	prescribed	no	no	no (rock)	yes (FLake 1D)		
RMIB-UGent	ALARO-0	Louis (1979)	ISBA (Noilhan & Planton, 1989)		2 levels	no			prescribed			no	no	no		
CLMcom-FZJ	COSMO5-01-CLM3-5-0-ParFlow3-9-0	Prognostic TKE / modified MY 2.5 (Raschendorfer, 2001)	Community Land Model v3.5, coupled via QASIS3-MCT2 with COSMO; coupling via exchange coefficients and surface variables	either from standalone Community Land Model + ParFlow hydrologic model or from fully coupled model; need about 10 years spinup minimum	15 layers; increasing depth from 0.02m at land surface to 15m at model bottom; total depth is -60m	no	no, constant, Tanré	1368 Wm-2	prescribed	prescribed, treatment t.b.d.	prescribed in CLM3.5	no	no	no	yes	
HCLIMcom-SMHI, HCLIMcom-DMI, HCLIMcom-MetNo	HCLIM43-ALADIN	CBR (Cuxart et al., 2000)	SURFEX (ECOCLIMAP-SG, GMTED2010 topo, SOILGRID soil texture) and ISBA-ES 12 layer snow scheme	Start 1950-08-01	ISBA-DIF: 0.01 m first, 12 m total, 14 layers	no	yes	1366 Wm-2	prescribed	Simple Ice (SICE)	no	no	TEB	FLAKE	no	Evaluation of individual and combined parameter settings (expert judgement). No specific optimization.
AUTH, NORCE/BCCR, CESAM, IDL, UCAN/IFCA, IMWM/CI TASK	WRF4.4.2 (t.b.d)	MYNN 2.5 (Nakanishi and Niino, 2009)	Noah-MP (Niu et al. 2011)	10 years land spin up with Noah-MP offline or/and 1 year land-atmosphere spin up with Noah-MP/WRF (t.b.d)	0.01 m depth of 1st layer, 2m in total, 4 layers	no	yes	1368.22 W	prescribed	prescribed	no (treated in Noah-MP LSM)	no	no	no	no	
AUTH	WRF4.?	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	NOAH LSM: 0.1m, 4 layers	no	yes (MERRA2 for eval runs, GCM-aerosol-forcing for hist/projections)		prescribed	prescribed		no	tbd	yes	t.b.d.	

institution_id institution

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CITASK Centre of Informatics Tricity Academic Supercomputer and network, Poland

CNRM Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques, Météo-France, CNRS

GERICS Climate Service Center Germany, Hamburg, Germany

ICTP International Center for Theoretical Physics, Trieste, Italy

IDL Instituto Dom Luiz, Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal

IMWM Institute of Meteorology and Water Management, Poland

KNMI Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute, Netherlands

MOHC Met Office

NORCE Norwegian Research Centre and Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research

RMIB-UGent Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium - University Ghent

Version	Date	Comment
0.1	2023-10-05	Initial version